

The Phenomenological Power of the Word in the Broken Voice

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“There is no longer any need to obey the Socratic precept ‘Know thyself’; it is enough merely to cry.”

Michel Henry¹

The question of power gained significant traction in the 20th-century as the focus shifted towards analysing disciplinary power from a postmodern perspective, moving away from a traditional view of power towards a kind of power that arises in different relationships. Foucault writes that his objective “has been to create a history of the different modes by which, in our culture, human beings are made subjects.”² The link between subjectivity and power is crucial. Long before our post-modern condition, this was effectively expressed in the encounter between the 1st-century Roman governor Pontius Pilate and Christ in the Gospels. This memorable meeting has been the theme of many works of art, such as the oil painting by the Russian painter Nikolai Nikolaevich, produced in 1890, titled “*What is Truth?*” *Christ and Pilate*. The painting shows the Roman governor standing in the light with his back to the viewer, gesturing with his hand – a sign of authority, confidence, and power, as he addresses Christ, who stands silently in the darkest part of the image, with his hands hidden behind his back, a sign of brokenness, powerlessness, and fragility.

¹ Michel Henry, *The Genealogy of Psychoanalysis*, trans. Douglas Brick (Stanford, California: Stanford University Press, 1993), 177–178.

² Michel Foucault, “The Subject and Power,” in *Beyond Structuralism and Hermeneutics*, ed. H. Dreyfus and P. Rabinow (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1983), 208–226.

This momentous meeting culminates in the 19th chapter of John's Gospel, which continues this dialogue between the two after Pilate took Jesus and had him flogged. Following this, we hear of the infamous utterance "*Ecce homo*" when Pilate presents a scourged Jesus, bound and crowned with thorns, to a hostile crowd shortly before his crucifixion. This escalates to Pilate's question: "Don't you realise I have power either to free you or to crucify you?" to which Jesus replies: "You would have no power over me if it were not given to you from above."³ This answer confounds Pilate, as his hesitation, uneasiness, and nervousness become evident as the fragile words of the accused disrupt and shake Pilate's worldly power and pride.

Inspired by this encounter, in this paper titled *The Phenomenological Power of the Word in the Broken Voice*, I will first examine what the 20th-century school known as phenomenology is and does, and how it contributes to this theological and philosophical notion of brokenness and power. Phenomenology, as a philosophical school of thought born and bred at the turn of the 20th century, contributes something unique to this ongoing discussion regarding the in-between of the post-traditional and the post-secular. This is made even more explicit with the advent of the so-called "Theological Turn" in the French intellectual scene, which brings a theologically driven notion of givenness into phenomenology. Here, I will specifically draw insights from Michel Henry and Jean-Louis Chrétien, who play a pivotal role in this turn, by expounding on the phenomenological power of the Word, which is at the heart of their work. Then, I will investigate the fragility of the voice and its power to bear witness and testify to the truth. In light of this, I will attempt to address the following questions: Does the broken voice retain the power to convey the Word of truth and life? Is the phenomenological experience of the Word transformative? Does our speech depend solely on ourselves? If not, whence do our utterances originate? What I aim to show is that the persisting vulnerability of our broken voice wounds our pride and unmasks our self-deception, exposing our dependence on the presence of the Arch-word – the Word of Life – which persists in turning our world upside down as it speaks into our human condition.

Phenomenological Theology

At the dawn of the 20th century, Edmund Husserl, an Austrian German philosopher and mathematician, called for a new fundamental science – 'pure

3 John 19:10–11 (NRSV).

phenomenology’ – which he believed was equally rigorous in method as all the other modern sciences. He identifies this new philosophy as a fundamental “science of origins,”⁴ an urgent call for all philosophical and scientific disciplines to be rooted within it to obtain their proper force and status. This becomes possible by adopting the phenomenological attitude, which, in turn, exposes the invisible dimensions of life.

Ultimately, Husserl believes phenomenology provides a rigorous method for describing the self. His major works demonstrate a profound concern with salvaging the self from being completely lost in the world, where it is taken for granted and left unexplored due to the radicalisation of positivism and naturalism. Husserl’s primary concern is that we go about our day-to-day life accepting a single spatiotemporal reality. He refers to this outlook as the ‘natural attitude.’ In this attitude, we naively consent that the visible world is merely present out there, whereby we encounter its presence without *thematizing* it, and, hence, without investigating the modes of appearance that structure subjectivity. In turn, Husserl claims a radical attitude shift from the meditating philosopher’s end is required. The phenomenological attitude can be seen as “the gate of entry to genuine knowledge of self and of the world.”⁵ He precisely saw himself fulfilling and revising the Cartesian project and the ancient Greek oracle “Know Thyself,” as made explicit in the concluding remark at the end of his 1929 Sorbonne lectures on Descartes’ Meditations:

The Delphic motto, “Know thyself!” has gained a new significance. Positive science is a science lost in the world. I must lose the world by epochē in order to regain it by a universal self-examination. “*Noli foras ire,*” says Augustine, “*in te redi, in interior homine habitat veritas.*”⁶

This view highlights the philosopher’s true mission, which is to satisfy an inner yearning and longing for the search for that which is behind the sensory world. Husserl’s phenomenological investigation precisely lies in exploring this

4 Edmund Husserl, *Ideas: General Introduction to Pure Phenomenology*, trans. W.R. Boyce Gibson (London: Routledge, 2002), §56, 110.

5 Edmund Husserl, *The Crisis of European Sciences and Transcendental Phenomenology*, trans. David Carr (Evanston: Northwestern University Press, 1970), 263.

6 Edmund Husserl, *Cartesian Meditations: An Introduction to Phenomenology*, trans. Dorion Cairns (The Hague: M. Nijhoff, 1960), 157. The translation of Augustine’s quote is “do not wish to go out, go back into yourself. Truth dwells in the inner man” from his work *De Vera Religione*, no.72. This echoes the Neoplatonic maxim, “Go back into yourself and look,” as found in Plotinus’ *Enneads*.

first-personal mode of givenness, which, in turn, opens the space of truth and interiority simultaneously. In another lecture in Vienna in 1935 on “Philosophy and the Crisis of European Man,” Husserl discussed the two distinct forms of sickness humans experience: the bodily and the spiritual. For the former, it is evident that the natural sciences have been progressing steadily and providing the right medicine that can cure various physical diseases. Husserl does not deny or undermine this advancement. However, he urges us to “turn our gaze from man’s body to his spirit, (which is) the theme of the so-called humanistic sciences.”⁷ Husserl’s point is that, whilst the notions of health and sickness are taken very seriously in the natural sciences, the humanistic sciences seem to lack the ability to deal with their illnesses and provide the proper antidotes.

In this sense, a humanistic science cannot satisfy itself with mere empirical observations or stop at the psychophysical level. According to Husserl, it must *not* be a science of nature but *a science of the spirit*. He maintains that studying the human spirit using natural science methods would be a grave mistake since the spirit is real in a different sense than nature. When this remains unacknowledged, the crisis of the spirit ensues precisely in its absorption into naturalism and objectivism. This approach has been reinforced with the rise of modern science, which views itself as having the only adequate tools and methods that lead towards the ultimate truth. However, the naturalist is limited to the physical world, leaving out or undermining the “inner life of the spirit”⁸ – what Husserl elsewhere also refers to as the “spiritual subject.”⁹ His riveting concluding words from his Vienna lecture are as follows:

The crisis of European existence can end in only one of two ways: in the ruin of a Europe alienated from its rational sense of life, fallen into a barbarian hatred of spirit; or in the rebirth of Europe from the spirit of philosophy, through a heroism of reason that will definitively overcome naturalism. Europe’s greatest danger is weariness. Let us as “good Europeans” do battle with this danger of dangers with the sort of courage that does not shirk even the endless battle. If we do, then from the annihilating conflagration of disbelief, from the fiery torrent

7 Edmund Husserl, “Philosophy and the Crisis of European Man,” in *Phenomenology and the Crisis of Philosophy*, trans. *Quentin Lauer*, (New York: Harper & Row, 1965), 149–50.

8 Husserl, “Philosophy and the Crisis of European Man,” 192.

9 Edmund Husserl, *Ideas II: Studies in the Phenomenology of Constitution*, trans. Richard Rojcewicz and André Schuwer (Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1989), §55, 227.

of despair regarding the West's mission to humanity, from the ashes of the great weariness, the phoenix of a new inner life of the spirit will arise as the underpinning of a great and distant human future, for the spirit alone is immortal.¹⁰

Ultimately, phenomenology seeks to redefine philosophy as an extensive and far-reaching investigation of human life by encompassing the sociopolitical, spiritual, artistic, and cultural spheres. As a result, phenomenology reopens the notion of experience, incorporating themes such as the sacred, the aesthetic, perception, language, and the body. This means that, for phenomenologists, conscious experience is a multifaceted and rich sphere where believing, loving, hoping, feeling, willing, imagining, perceiving, sensing, remembering, attending, anticipating, and all other acts are accomplished, and the space within which the meaning of such acts is revealed. The phenomenological attitude invites us to become more than mere participants in the world by contemplating our participation and engaging with the knowledge we hold. In 2018, Emmanuel Falque, a French Catholic theologian and philosopher whose work synthesises medieval theology, philosophy of religion, and French phenomenology, made the following statement about the enduring fascination with phenomenology:

The attractiveness of phenomenology, in France but also in the United States, comes from its capacity for crossing different fields and its capacity for returning to our lived experience. Phenomenology attempts to be “near to things,” “near to others,” “near to the world,” and even “near to God,” because it endeavours to describe “the things themselves,” in order to return to Husserl’s first imperative, rather than to separate reality into abstract concepts. It is because phenomenology is living and speaks of the “world of life” that it remains relevant. This is also what gives phenomenology an affinity with patristic and medieval philosophy, because there too it is life that is always first.¹¹

After Husserl, philosophical discourse underwent a transformation, becoming attuned to new possibilities. As a result, later thinkers struggled to continue

¹⁰ Husserl, “Philosophy and the Crisis of European Man,” 192.

¹¹ Emmanuel Falque, “Christ Doesn’t Save Us by Words First of All, but by His Body,” interview by Artur Rosman, *Church Life Journal*, June 07, 2018, accessed on 15 March 2025, <https://churchlifejournal.nd.edu/articles/christ-doesnt-save-us-by-words-first-of-all-but-by-his-body/>

widening and challenging the limits and boundaries set by previous philosophers. French thinkers, such as Jean-Luc Marion, Michel Henry, and Jean-Louis Chrétien, will eventually generate the so-called “Theological Turn” within phenomenology.¹² Their approach rests on the notion that philosophical discourse can describe religious phenomena without having to withdraw claims about the absolute and the irreducible. Indeed, they are concerned with opening up phenomenology to an even broader spectrum of human experiences: love, grace, hope, faith, suffering, joy, touch, humility, and the like. In such a phenomenological theology, God is portrayed as pure love and a giver, interested in the human condition with all its fragility and finiteness.

Such a God is embraced as an absolutely self-given, pure gift of love in Marion;¹³ the One who summons me in the voice and touch of the Other in Chrétien; and as the One who, according to Henry, claims all humanity as His own ‘sons’ in accordance to the ‘Truth of Life.’¹⁴ What characterises the movement of these radical phenomenologists is precisely the fact that they are not concerned with metaphysics, or onto-theology, to come to terms with an omnipotent and omniscient, self-sufficient God. In this sense, phenomenology aids the theologian not in his arguments to prove God’s existence but in the discourse about lived experience. Thus, phenomenological theology helps to articulate the moods, manifestations, and bodily experiences of the believer’s life of faith.

Henry, whose final works consist of a trilogy on a phenomenology of Christianity, aims to move beyond rational argumentation as a means to demonstrate the existence of God since, according to him, demanding “a proof of God’s existence means to put God on trial in the world, to subject him to the obligation to appear according to this mode of appearing that is the light of this world, the ek-stasy of exteriority, where things and ideas are shown.”¹⁵ His

12 See Dominique Janicaud, “The Theological Turn of French Phenomenology,” in *Phenomenology and the “Theological Turn”: The French Debate*, trans. Bernard G. Prusak (New York: Fordham University Press, 2000).

13 In Marion’s phenomenology, such a gift is not presented with the expectation of repayment, thus going against any form of economic logic. It is simply pure givenness (hence, donation) without any return. See Jean-Luc Marion, *Givenness and Revelation*, trans. Stephen E. Lewis, (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016).

14 See J. Aaron Simmons, “God in Recent French Phenomenology,” in *Philosophy Compass* 3, no. 5 (2008): 910–932, doi: 10.1111/j.1747–9991.2008.00171.x.

15 Michel Henry, *I am the Truth: Toward a Philosophy of Christianity*, trans. Susan Emanuel (Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 2003), 156.

work explores a language that does not originate in the world but, instead, from the “other site where the Word of Life speaks.”¹⁶ According to Henry, religion today faces scepticism precisely because this distinction is left unacknowledged, leading to “ruinous confusion.”¹⁷ Moreover, he maintains that “religion does not belong to the human as a singular experience but as its essence. It designates the inner connection of the living to the life from which it derives its connection as alive, in which it experiences (*éprouve*) all that it experiences.”¹⁸ This means that if experiences remain trapped within the world’s truth, they lose their power to reclaim another kind of truth. Failing to acknowledge this distinction leads to the belief that what is given is always presented from a single viewpoint – as an object-in-the-world, hence as exteriority. Instead, we need to “elevate the human spirit by detaching it from worldly affairs, whose trademark is transience and vanity, in order to open it to what alone matters.”¹⁹

When the flickering light of the world is diminished, the Word of Life appears under its own terms. In turn, this opens up a new way of knowing, indicating that “it is not thought that gives us access to life, (rather) it is Life that gives us access to thought, in as much as thought is only a mode of life.”²⁰ In this knowledge of Life, we come upon something inherently other-than-being-in-the-world, which is a deeper awareness of one’s being and that of others, and not more information about anything or anyone. In this sense, the Word of Life is not just a symbolic or descriptive tool, but the power of creation, since the Word is the internal expression of God’s being.

The Word of Life in the Broken Voice

And yet, this powerful Word assumes our fragility in the kenotic act of the Incarnation. Jean-Louis Chrétien, a French poet and phenomenologist who forms a crucial part of the aforementioned Theological Turn, elucidates this through his phenomenology of fragility, whereby the Word of Life assumes the

16 Ibid., 230–31.

17 Ibid. 153.

18 Michel Henry, “Difficult Democracy,” in *The Michel Henry Reader*, ed. Scott Davidson and Frederic Seyler (Evanston: Illinois: Northwestern University Press, 2019), 169.

19 Michel Henry, *Words of Christ*, trans. Christina M. Gschwandtner, (Michigan: Wm B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 2012), 93.

20 Michel Henry, *Incarnation*, trans. Karl Hefty (Evanston, Illinois: Northwestern University Press, 2015), 254.

fragility of our body as the servitude of our human condition.²¹ Chrétien stressed that, against the concept of finitude, which remains an abstraction, the term fragility is more adequate in its distinct meaning; a notion in philosophy which has often been marginalised and impoverished in its meaning. Fragility is frequently contrasted with toughness, stability, boldness, and power. However, this is a false opposition, which undermines the singularity of fragility. In fact, what makes fragility such a rich concept from a Christian perspective is that it escapes this opposition.

Fragility is a permanent condition inscribed in our being. It attests to our unique way of being, which is susceptible to breaking according to its structure. Fragility is a profound memento of our weakness, which remains present even when it is unacknowledged or masked by worldly power and pride. In this sense, it is closest to vulnerability, whose Latin origin, *vulner*, means “wound.” Being vulnerable also means being exposed. This reverberates beautifully with the Early Middle Ages philosopher Boethius’s dialogue with Lady Philosophy, when she expresses the following statement in his final hours: “If you want the doctor’s help, you must reveal the wound.”²² This condition of being wounded and fragile exposes our dependence on the care of others, creating both the possibility and the necessity of trustful relationships. This means that rather than being equated to a flaw, fragility must be understood as the foundation of compassion and solidarity.

Yet, pride and worldly power make us forgetful of our fragility by claiming to bequeath on us a divine immunity, forgetting or unacknowledging that we are fragile at the core of our being. Humility, unlike pride, is thus necessary to actively conform to the Word of Life. Gabriel Marcel, in his Gifford Lectures, claims that “at the root of humility lies the more or less unexpressed assertion, ‘By myself, I am nothing and I can do nothing.’”²³ Humility is not a quality but a mode of being, which includes the recognition of the creature’s nothingness and the affirmation of the sacred. Henry similarly claims that “it is here that the pretension of human thought to attain Truth by the force of its own thinking goes up in smoke.”²⁴ Resonating with both Marcel and Henry is also Dietrich

21 See Jean-Louis Chrétien, *Fragilité* (Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit, 2017).

22 Boethius, *The Consolation of Philosophy*, trans. Victor Watts (London: Penguin Books, 1969), 9.

23 Gabriel Marcel, *The Mystery of Being II: Faith and Reality*, trans. R. Hague, (London: The Harvill Press Ltd., 1951), 85–86. ‘Faith and Reality’ contains the second of the two series of Gifford Lectures given by Marcel at the University of Aberdeen in 1949 and 1950.

24 Henry, *Incarnation*, 255.

von Hildebrand, who examines this virtue of humility as an affective experience which is brought about by “a melting of one’s hardheartedness or insipidity, a surrender in the face of great and noble things which call for tears.”²⁵ This centrality of humility entails, for Hildebrand, that “what is true of love – that without it, all other virtues and good works are valueless – is again, in another respect, true on humility.”²⁶

In turn, pride contaminates our inner dispositions by taking the form of self-glorification and confines us within a world which allows no other reference points outside itself. In this sense, pride can be understood as akin to what Charles Taylor describes as the “buffered subject,”²⁷ locked in oneself (*incurvatus in se*). Marcel rightfully maintains that “as for pride, it consists in drawing one’s strength solely from oneself. The proud man is cut off from a certain form of communion with his fellow men, which pride, acting as a principle of destruction, tends to break down.”²⁸ This is because pride, by dethroning humility, yearns for self-supremacy, leaving no room or space for genuine self-transformation. In other words, rather than being the foundation of myself, I am grounded in the power of the Word of Life. In turn, this allows me to become more attuned to others who share the same power and source.

In light of this, rather than separating us from God’s perfection and infinite power, human fragility, which is acknowledged through humility, can be better understood as the privileged site where God, as the Word of Life, approaches and visits us. Brokenness, then, is a phenomenal experience of God’s presence. As noted, the Incarnation is key here, for it is in the Incarnation of the Word of Life that comes to inhabit human fragility and transfigure it. In the Incarnation of the Word, human fragility is portrayed as something God cherished and embraced, elevating the aspects of the creaturely condition it is tied to, imbuing them with dignity that transcends contempt. Thus, the broken voice is an authentic encounter with God’s reality. In its fragility, it becomes an affirmation of life. In its vulnerability, it expresses a deep yearning for divine assistance. As Chrétien also writes, “it is when I myself do not make myself strong and

25 Dietrich von Hildebrand, *The Heart. An Analysis of Human and Divine Affectivity*, ed. J. H. Crosby (Indiana: St. Augustine’s Press, 2007),-10.

26 Dietrich von Hildebrand, *Transformation in Christ* (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 2001), 149.

27 Charles Taylor, *A Secular Age* (Cambridge, Massachusetts: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2007), 300.

28 Gabriel Marcel, *The Philosophy of Existentialism* (New York: The Citadel Press, 1970), 32.

recognise my fragility that the strength of God has the space to deploy within me and throughout me”²⁹

This entails that the way we deal with our fragility matters. Suppressing this fragility by overcoming or escaping it through cultivating inner strength and pride makes us believe that, through our own power, we can become invulnerable. On the other hand, recognising our brokenness and fragility without redirecting it and, instead, allowing it to become our goal and sole reality, leads to despair. This would, in turn, shatter us and throw us into nihilism, where everything becomes vain and futile. The third way is the path towards a transfiguration of this brokenness. Since this condition has already been embraced by the Word of Life and transformed within God’s redemptive plan, it is given a new meaning. Through the Incarnate Word, who has been “crushed for our iniquities” (Isaiah 53:5), brokenness can be experienced or navigated with renewed strength and a new purpose rather than defeated or abandoned. In turn, brokenness became the very site of salvation. This entails that, where brokenness is, salvation is also present. By the resurrection, new hope is breathed into our very own brokenness. All this resonates with what the Apostle Paul writes in his second letter to the church in Corinth, specifically the 9th verse in chapter 12, which speaks of God’s grace being sufficient and how God’s strength is made perfect in human weakness.

With all this in mind, does our speech and voice, hence the power to speak and utter words, depend solely on ourselves? If that were the case, then death would have the final say. However, if we reject this as incomplete, whence do our utterances originate? The answer lies in the power of the Word of Life that has spoken its creative power before we came to be and will continue to do so after drawing our final breath. This means our fragile voice is neither an original speech nor the last word. Our words are sustained by the Word of Life that, through the Incarnation, models our salvation history. In turn, the persisting vulnerability of our broken and fragile voice wounds our pride and unmasks our self-deception, exposing our dependence on the presence of the Arch-word – the Word of Life – which speaks both before us and into our human condition, as it persists in turning our world upside down.

Ultimately, God’s presence depends not on what we say but on the authenticity of our heart, as the interior space that humbly acknowledges we

29 Jean-Louis Chrétien, *Under the Gaze of the Bible* (New York: Fordham University Press, 2015), 76.

would have no power by ourselves if it were not given to us from above.³⁰ This dependence is again captured in Christ's words when he claims that "whenever you are arrested and brought to trial, do not worry beforehand about what to say. Just say whatever is given you at the time, for it is not you speaking, but the Holy Spirit."³¹ This condition of 'being arrested and brought to trial' – which exemplifies the Christian way of being in the world – highlights our state of vulnerability and brokenness, a condition shared with the Incarnate Word as portrayed in the painting of Christ and Pilate, mentioned in the introduction to this paper. Hence, this fragile state is not a problem to be solved or fixed, but the very site where the Power of the Word manifests itself, in which we are rooted, and without which we can say or do nothing by ourselves. This power increases in proportion to letting go of the idea of ourselves as absolutely autonomous individuals and admitting our state of fragility and vulnerability. This resonates beautifully in the words of John the Baptist when he firmly states: "No one can receive anything except what has been given from heaven. (...) He must increase, but I must decrease."³²

Conclusion

If we are fragile, won't our speech bear the stamp of this brokenness, and won't it thereby be worthless to bear witness and testify to the truth? As argued throughout, the persisting vulnerability of our brokenness wounds our pride and unmasks our self-deception, exposing our dependence on the power of the Arch-word, the Word of Life, which speaks into our human condition. The broken voice signifies not a failure to express the truth but rather its authentic form. This is made possible since the Word of Life has taken on flesh anew amid human fragility. Viewed from a phenomenological lens, this invites us to encounter the divine not with clarity or control, but through our fragile speech that reveals the sacred as both present and elusive. For theology, this voice deepens the significance of the Word, illustrating that the divine often communicates most powerfully through human vulnerability. Thus, the broken voice serves not as a disruption, but as a revelation, a space where the Word of Life resonates most faithfully through the fractures of human existence.

30 See John 19:10–11 (NRSV).

31 See Mark 13:11 (NRSV).

32 See John 3:27–11 (NRSV).

This brokenness, far from being a limitation, becomes the very condition under which divine manifestation occurs. Hence, our woundedness is both a mark of our fragile condition and a site of grace. In this way, the broken voice enacts a truth that cannot be possessed but is received from above. This also entails that the broken voice is not subordinate to theological discourse. Instead, it is its beating heart. Through the shattered edges of language and life, we are drawn closer to the mystery we persistently seek to articulate. In the end, the Word of Life does not bypass human weakness but inhabits it, speaks through it, and is heard most truly in its trembling voice.

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